

THE EFFECT OF MACRO AND MICRO FERTILIZERS USED IN COTTON ON THE DYNAMICS OF SOIL NUTRIENTS

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Abstract. *The article describes the results of scientific research on the effect of the new type of "Kafolon" with microelements made from local raw materials and liquid simple and complex fertilizers on the agrochemical properties of the soil, in particular, on the changes in the dynamics of exchangeable potassium and the mobile form of nitrogen and phosphorus in the soil.*

Keywords: *agrochemical properties, mobile nitrogen, mobile phosphorus, exchangeable potassium, trace elements, fertilizers.*

Relevance of the topic. It is known that in cotton growing, it is important to create varieties resistant to various external factors, resistant to diseases and insects, to develop special agrotechnologies for their care, and to obtain a fabulous, high-quality harvest even in any soil and climatic conditions.

Taking this into account, it is important to develop optimal terms and standards for applying new types of liquid fertilizers containing microelements to cotton, created by scientists and specialists of our republic and produced in other countries, in order to increase productivity.

Development of the technology of foliar application of macro- and micro-fertilizers in appropriate proportions, convenient time, norms and methods for growing high and quality cotton crops in the conditions of carbonate soils of our republic lacking in microelements is one of the urgent issues of the agricultural sector, and now carrying out a scientific research to study this issue is going to be important.

Research object. The field experiment was conducted at the PSUEAITI experimental site under typical gray soil conditions.

Research method. Before the field experiment, samples of the 0-30, 30-50 cm layers of the soil are taken from the field using the envelope method. The mobile forms of humus, nitrogen, phosphorus, total potassium and NPK were determined in the obtained soil samples.

The agrochemical analysis of the soil samples obtained from the field experiments was determined according to the methods, "Methods of agrochemical, agrophysical and microbiological research in irrigated cotton areas " and " Methods of agrochemical analysis of soils and plants of Central Asia".

Research results. When the S-4727 variety of cotton is grown in the alluvial soils of the irrigated meadow of Khorezm region, the cotton plant produces 0.034-0.088 kg/ha of copper from one hectare, and 0.002-0.070 kg/ha of copper corresponds to the cotton yield, with a vegetative mass of 0.029-0.086 kg/ha cotton, stems and pods, leaves and roots. Zinc is removed by more cotton parts than copper, and 0.144-0.178 kg of zinc per hectare is absorbed in one season.

The largest amount of zinc is in the roots - 0.032-0.053 kg/ha returns to the soil. The total amount of manganese removed by cotton parts was 0.106-0.932 kg per hectare. If more than 50% of micronutrients are returned with leaves, their balance is high, and if it is less than 50%, the soil

is poor with micronutrients in mobile form and requires the use of microfertilizers [1]. Against the background of mineral fertilizers N-200, P₂O₅-140, K₂O-100 kg/ha, the relatively optimal effect of Baikal EM-1 microbiological fertilizer on the agrochemical properties of the soil 10.0 l/ha before autumn plowing, 10.0 l/ha in spring over plowing, 3.0 l/ha is obtained when cotton is applied during the period of 2-3 true leaves and 3.5 l/ha - during the flowering period; during the flowering period of cotton, the amount of nitrate nitrogen in the plow (0-30 cm) and sub-plot (30-50 cm) layers of the soil is equal to 23.1-10.1 mg/kg, and mobile phosphorus is 24.5-11.0 mg/kg and 3.3-0.1 of the control with exchangeable potassium 255-185 mg/kg; 1.8-0.5 and 20.0-5.0 mg/kg were found to be higher [2].

It is known that for many years growth regulators have been widely tested in cotton farming and other areas of agriculture, and recommendations have been given on their use in the optimal period and standards, but it is urgent to carry out scientific research on determining the biological effectiveness of new types of liquid fertilizers with microelements in cotton. N-150, P₂O₅-105, K₂O-75 kg/ha in system 1 of the field experiment, N-200, P₂O₅-140, K₂O-100 kg/ha in system 2, N-250, P₂O₅-175, K₂O in system 3 -125 kg/ha of fertilizers are included. In series 1, 2, 3 "Kafolon" (Immunity (N, K, Mg, Ca, S, Fe, Cu, Zn, Si), Pitane and Finish (N, K, Mg, Ca, S, Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn, V, Co, B) micronutrient fertilizers; liquid trace elements (total water-soluble boron-(B) 0.2%, iron (Fe) 2%, zinc (Zn) 3%, manganese (Mn)-1%, copper(Cu) 0.5%, total amino acid 2%, pH 2-4); Liquid NPK fertilizer and trace elements (total nitrogen (N) 16.0%, urea 8.8%, nitrate nitrogen 2.4%, ammonium nitrogen 4.8%, total phosphorus (P₂O₅) 16.0%, total potassium (K₂O) 12.0%), total water-soluble boron-(B) 0.02%, iron (Fe) 0.10%, manganese (Mn)-0.05%, copper (Cu) 0.05% liquid macro and micro-fertilizers are also given and their norms and terms are the same. In order to determine the effect of liquid simple and complex fertilizers on changes in agrochemical properties of the soil when cotton is fed through the leaf, a new type of "Kafolon" with microelements made from local raw materials and the effect of using different micronutrient suspensions on the dynamics of nitrate form of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium in the soil was studied against the background of 3 different standards of mineral fertilizers. The obtained data are presented in tables.

First of all, it should be said that when the rate of mineral fertilizers increases from N₁₅₀, P₁₀₅, K₇₅ g/ha to nitrogen N₂₀₀ P₁₄₀, K₁₀₀ and N₂₅₀, P₁₇₅, K₁₂₅kg/ha, the amount of nitrogen in the form of nitrate in the soil increases (decrease from 0-100 cm), moreover, it was observed that these indicators increase again from spring to summer and decrease in autumn. We confirm that it depends on the increase in soil temperature and nitrogen uptake by plants (Table 1).

In option 1 (control), where microelements were not applied, the amount of nitrate nitrogen in 0-30 and 30-50 cm layers of the soil was 17.0-13.2, in proportion to the periods of cotton development; 18.6-13.6; 19.8-14.4 and 17.8-12.0 mg/kg, it was found that the amount of N-NO₃ in the soil during the flowering period of cotton was increased by 3.0 mg/kg from the initial state at the end of the period of application of cotton, when the set of trace elements known as "Kafolon" (by "KIMYO UZ") was applied as a liquid suspension through the leaf to the experimental system. It was 21.9-15.6 mg/g in the 0-30 and 30-50 cm layers, and 19.6-13.2 mg/g in ripening, and 2.1-1.2 and 1.8 proportionally more than the control. It was found to be higher than -1.2 mg/g. This situation indicates that when the complex of microelements is applied through the leaves, the physiological processes in cotton are improved, and the metabolism is improved due to the increase in the rate of photosynthesis. Relatively better indicators are obtained under the influence

of liquid NPK fertilizers with a complex of microelements belonging to "Ifoda" organization. In this variant (4), during cotton flowering, the amount of nitrate nitrogen in the 0-30 and 30-50 cm layers of the soil is proportionately 23.6-16.2 mg/kg, and 20.6-13.6 mg/kg during ripening. It was found that it increased by 3.8-1.8 and 2.8-1.6 mg/kg from the control and 8.8-9.5 and 5.8-6.9 mg/kg from the initial state.

In the 5th (control) variant, where the rate of mineral fertilizers was N₂₀₀, P₁₄₀, K₁₀₀ kg/kg, the amount of nitrate nitrogen in the 0-30 and 30-50 cm layers of the soil was proportionate to (during cotton flowering) 21.0-15.1 mg/kg, and (at ripening) in the amount of 18.6-12.6 mg/kg, fertilizers N₁₅₀, P₁₀₅, K₇₅ kg/ha were applied at the rate of 1.2-0.7 mg/kg and 0.8-0.6 mg/kg was found to be higher.

Table 1.

Dynamics of nitrate nitrogen in soil, (mg/kg), 2022

Variant order	2-3 true leaves				Blooming				Flowering				Ripening			
	Soil layer, <u>sm</u>															
	0-30	30-50	50-70	70-100	0-30	30-50	50-70	70-100	0-30	30-50	50-70	70-100	0-30	30-50	50-70	70-100
Background – N-150, P₂O₅-105, K₂O -75 kg/ha																
1	17,0	13,2	10,0	6,0	18,6	13,6	10,2	6,2	19,8	14,4	10,6	6,6	17,8	12,0	8,8	6,2
2	18,6	13,8	10,6	6,2	20,5	14,9	11,1	6,4	21,9	15,6	11,5	6,8	19,6	13,2	11,0	6,4
3	18,4	14,2	11,0	6,6	21,0	15,0	11,3	6,8	23,2	16,0	11,8	7,4	20,4	13,4	11,2	7,0
4	18,2	14,0	11,2	6,4	21,4	15,2	11,5	6,6	23,6	16,2	12,0	7,6	20,6	13,6	11,4	7,2
Background – N-200, P₂O₅-140, K₂O-100 kg/ha																
5	17,6	13,4	10,4	6,2	20,6	14,5	10,6	7,4	21,0	15,1	11,0	7,8	18,6	12,6	9,2	7,4
6	18,8	14,0	10,5	6,4	22,5	15,2	11,6	7,5	23,1	17,1	12,2	8,0	20,5	14,5	11,4	7,5
7	19,4	13,6	10,6	6,3	23,6	15,4	11,7	7,7	24,2	17,5	12,4	8,2	20,7	15,0	11,6	7,7
8	19,2	13,8	10,7	6,5	24,8	15,6	11,8	7,9	25,1	17,7	12,6	8,4	20,9	15,2	11,8	7,9
Background – N-250, P₂O₅-175, K₂O-125 kg/ha																
9	17,5	13,2	10,5	6,0	22,1	14,7	10,8	7,5	23,0	16,6	11,0	7,8	21,6	14,6	9,4	7,5
10	20,6	14,6	11,0	6,4	23,4	15,4	11,8	7,7	24,6	17,6	12,5	8,0	22,0	15,0	11,6	7,6
11	21,0	15,0	11,2	6,6	24,2	15,6	11,9	7,9	25,1	17,8	12,7	8,2	22,2	15,2	11,7	7,8
12	21,2	15,2	11,4	6,8	24,4	15,8	12,0	8,0	25,2	18,0	12,8	8,4	22,4	15,4	11,9	8,0

It should be noted that as the rate of mineral fertilizers increased, the effect of applied microelements (complex) on the change of nitrate nitrogen in the soil was relatively reduced. In the 8th option, which is considered acceptable, at the end of the cotton period, the above indicators are proportional to 20.9-15.2 mg/kg, are different compared to its control (5 var) by 2.3-2.6 mg/kg and the initial state by 6.1 -8.5 mg/kg, which is 0.3-1.6 mg/kg less than the indicators of option 4. In the experiment, relatively high indicators were obtained in options 9-12, where mineral fertilizers N₂₅₀, P₁₇₅, K₁₂₅ m/kg were used, while in the control, the above indicators were proportional to 21.6-14.6 mg/kg at the end of the cotton season, and the ratio of option 1 was 3 ,8-2.6 mg/kg and 3.0-2.0 mg/kg higher than option 5.

So, due to the increase in fertilizer rates, the amount of nitrate nitrogen increased from the initial state changed proportionally (var 1, 5 and 9) to 3.0-(5.3) mg/kg, 3.8-(5.9) mg/kg and 6, 8-(7.9) mg/kg, and under the influence of microelements it changed 2.8--1.8; 2.3-1.9; it was found that it increased by 0.8-0.4 mg/kg, in which case it was observed that the effect of fertilizer rates was 2-3 times higher. The dynamics of mobile phosphorus in the soil is similar to that of nitrate nitrogen, and with changes in soil temperature and increase in fertilizer rates, it is also observed to differ among variants and across periods of cotton development (Table 2).

Mineral fertilizers N₁₅₀, P₁₀₅, K₇₅ kg/ha, N₂₀₀, P₁₄₀, K₁₀₀ kg/ha and N₂₅₀, P₁₇₅, K₁₂₅ kg/ha (without micronutrients) were used in control (1, 5 and 9) variants 0-30 and 30-50 cm layers of the soil 17.8, 15.2; 19.1; 15.3; 20.1; 15.9 mg/kg in 2-3 true leaves of cotton; 20.1; 16.0; 21.6; 16.1; 25.2; 16.8 mg/kg, the amount of P₂O₅ during flowering period is proportional to 20.5; 16.4; 23.5; 16.6; and 25.5; 17.0 mg/kg, and 17.2 -15.2 at the end of the period; 19.5-15.6 and 21.8-16.4 mg/kg were analyzed.

These indicators show that with an increase in the rate of fertilizers, the amount of P₂O₅ in the driving layer of the soil (0-30 cm) is proportional to 2.0, 3.5, 7.1 m/kg from the initial state; in flowering to 2.4; 5.4; 7.4mg/kg and in ripening (-0.9) to 1.4 and 3.7 mg/kg increase were found. In these variants (1.5 and 9) in 50-70 and 70-100 cm layers of the soil in 2-3 true leaves (11.2-12.0; 9.1-9.5 mg/kg), in combing (11.6 -12.3; 9.3-10.0 mg/kg), at flowering (11.7-12.4; 9.4-10.2 mg/kg), at ripening (11.0-12.2 and 9,0-9,9 mg/kg) was found to be provided at the lowest level.

It is worth noting that for every 100 kg of P₂O₅ applied to many years of research, soil phosphorus increases by 1.0 mg/kg. In this case, in 20-25 years, if the amount of phosphorus in the soil was - 15.0 mg/kg, +20-25 mg would be added and it would reach 35-40 mg/kg. However, the typical gray soils at the Cotton Institute have a low supply of mobile phosphorus, around 20-25 mg/kg.

Table 2

Dynamics of mobile phosphorus in soil, (mg/kg), 2022

Variant order	2-3 soft leaves				Blooming				Blossoming				Ripening			
	Soil layer, <i>sm</i>															
	0-30	30-50	50-70	70-100	0-30	30-50	50-70	70-100	0-30	30-50	50-70	70-100	0-30	30-50	50-70	70-100
Background – N-150, P₂O₅-105, K₂O-75 kg/ ha																
1	17,8	15,2	11,2	9,1	20,1	16,0	11,6	9,3	20,5	16,4	11,7	9,4	17,2	15,2	11,0	9,0
2	18,4	15,4	11,4	9,3	20,4	16,2	11,8	9,5	21,8	16,6	12,0	9,7	17,6	15,4	11,2	9,2
3	18,6	15,5	11,6	9,4	20,6	16,4	12,0	9,6	22,0	16,7	12,2	9,8	17,8	15,6	11,4	9,4
4	18,7	15,6	11,7	9,5	20,8	16,6	12,2	9,8	22,2	16,8	12,4	9,9	18,0	15,8	11,6	9,5
Background – N-200, P₂O₅-140, K₂O-100 kg/ha																
5	19,1	15,3	11,8	9,3	21,6	16,1	11,7	9,5	23,5	16,6	12,0	9,6	19,5	15,6	11,9	9,4
6	19,3	15,4	11,3	9,5	22,8	16,3	11,9	9,7	24,0	16,8	12,2	9,8	19,8	15,8	12,1	9,6
7	19,5	15,5	11,4	9,6	23,4	16,5	12,0	9,8	24,4	17,0	12,4	10,0	20,0	16,0	12,3	9,7
8	19,6	15,7	11,5	9,7	24,0	16,6	12,2	9,9	25,0	17,2	12,6	10,1	20,2	16,2	12,4	9,8
Background – N-250, P₂O₅-175, K₂O-125 kg/ha																
9	20,1	15,9	12,0	9,5	25,2	16,8	12,3	10,0	25,5	17,0	12,4	10,2	21,8	16,4	12,2	9,9
10	20,4	16,2	12,2	9,6	25,7	17,0	12,5	10,1	26,0	17,2	12,6	10,4	22,0	16,6	12,4	10,2
11	21,2	16,4	12,4	9,8	26,0	17,2	12,6	10,2	26,5	17,4	12,8	10,6	22,2	16,8	12,6	10,4
12	21,4	16,6	12,6	9,9	26,2	17,4	12,8	10,4	26,8	17,6	12,9	10,7	22,4	17,0	12,8	10,5

Due to this, fertilizer phosphorus goes through complex transformation processes when it enters the soil, primary phosphates pass to secondary and tertiary phosphates and turn into forms that are difficult for plants to absorb. Therefore, the problem of phosphorus application is considered an unfinished field.

However, in our experiment, it was observed that various water-soluble (chelated) trace elements used in the background of fertilizers had an acceptable effect on the dynamics of mobile phosphorus in the soil. However, their effect on phosphorus was found to be different from that of nitrate nitrogen. In other words, it was found that the effect of trace elements on phosphorus was relatively lower. Mineral fertilizers N₁₅₀, P₁₀₅, K₇₅ kg/ha are acceptable parameters against the background of liquid NPK fertilizers and microelements in the form of suspension in the 0-30 and

30-50 cm layers of the soil (during the tillering period), the amount of mobile phosphorus is proportional to 20.8-16.6 mg/ kg, (during flowering) 22.2-16.8 mg/kg, 0.7-0.6 of the control; increased by 1.7-0.4 mg/kg, it was found to decrease to 18.0-15.8 mg/kg at the end of the action period and differed by 0.8-0.6 mg/kg. However, nitrate nitrogen content (2.8-1.6 mg/kg) was higher.

In the parallel (same microelements) option, where the rate of mineral fertilizers is N₂₀₀, P₁₄₀, K₁₀₀ kg/kg, the above indicators are proportional to 24.0-16.6 mg/kg (in the setting), 25.0-17.2 mg/kg (in the flowering), and 20.2-16.2 mg/kg (ripening), 2.4-0.5 of the control; 1.5-0.6 and 0.7-0.6 mg/kg, and from the initial state to 6.9-8.0 mg/kg during the flowering period, it was analyzed that it increased to 2.1-7.0 mg/kg at the end of the effective period.

With an increase in the rate of mineral fertilizers N₂₅₀, P₁₇₅, K₁₂₅ kg/ha, the amount of mobile phosphorus under the influence of applied microelements (var 12) was proportional to 26.2 and 17.4 mg/kg during the flowering period and 26.8 and 17.6 mg/kg during the ripening period, 22.4 and 17.0 mg/kg in the ripening period, 1.0-0.6 of the control; and differed by 0.6-0.6 mg/kg. However, under the influence of (parallel) micronutrients (var 4) used against the background of N₁₅₀, P₁₀₅, K₇₅kg/ha, these changes are proportional to 0.7-0.6. It was differentiated by 1.7-0.4 mg/kg and 0.8-0.6 mg/kg. So, it was determined that the optimal effect of trace elements on the change of the amount of mobile phosphorus in the soil (such as nitrate nitrogen) was better compared to the background of fertilizers N₁₅₀, P₁₀₅, K₇₅ kg/ha.

It should be noted that the amount of exchangeable potassium in the soil also increases with the increase of parameters such as nitrate nitrogen and mobile phosphorus, and it is found that it increases from spring to summer and decreases towards autumn.

Therefore, with an increase in the rate of mineral fertilizers N₂₀₀, P₁₄₀, K₁₀₀ kg/ha, the above indicators are proportional to 270-166 in the plowing (0-30 cm) and lower (30-50 cm) layers of the soil during the 2-3rd leaf, tillering and flowering period; 290-180 and 296-184 mg/kg, 10-6 against option 1; 20-10 and 16.0-4.0 mg/kg, and 20-36 from the initial state. An increase of 40-50 and 46-54 mg/kg was observed. In the variant of this control (5), the soil in layers of 50-70 and 70-100cm should be treated with 2-3 leaves, combing, flowering and ripening at the lowest levels (124-82; 124-83, 126-84 and 124-84 mg/ kg) was found to be.

Relatively high indicators were used again in the norms of N₂₅₀, P₁₇₅, K₁₂₅kg/ha (control) in the 9th option, and at the end of the 2-3rd leaf, tillering, flowering, and the end of the period of operation, it was found that the plowing (0-30 cm) and the bottom (30-50 cm) of the soil was provided in medium levels (280-170; 296-190; 301-186 and 293-176 mg/kg). So it was observed that the change of exchangeable potassium amounts in the soil also depends on the fertilizer standards.

"Kafolon" set of microelements in the applied suspension improved the nutrition of cotton and had a favorable effect on the amount of exchangeable potassium in the soil.

Conclusion. In the background of mineral fertilizers N₁₅₀, P₁₀₅, K₇₅ kg/ha, when the suspension based on liquid NPK fertilizers with a complex of microelements is applied through the leaf during the development periods of cotton, the amount of nitrate nitrogen in the soil is proportional to 23.6-16.2 mg/kg at flowering in the 0-30 and 30-50 cm layers, and at ripening it was 20.6-13.6 mg/kg, 3.8-1.8 and 2.8-1.6 mg/kg higher than the control, and 8.8-9.5 and 5.8-6.9 mg/kg was found to be increased.

As a conclusion, it should be said that in the conditions of irrigated typical gray soils, against the background of different norms of mineral fertilizers, the application of micronutrients in suspension through leaves (as food) has an effect on the optimization of soil agrochemical (N-NO₃, P₂O₅, K₂O) properties.

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